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Less engaging products and society

I cautiously removed the precious gramophone record from its cover and placed it on the turntable. With the no-static brush I carefully removed the hardly visible dust particles. I lifted up the arm, gently blew a bit of fluff from the needle and moved it smoothly above the record. After a last check, I carefully placed the needle in the groove. A soft tick, a cracking noise, and a few seconds later the beautiful voice of Mathilde Santing filled the room.

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I hardly use my record player anymore. Several years ago, I yielded to the tempting quality of sound and bought a CD player. The voice of Santing is now written on a silver disc, which is tucked inside a black box with several anonymous buttons. Although the sound has improved, I do miss the subtlety of interaction that enhanced my experience of listening.

Technology brought us many new possibilities and advantages, also in the field of consumer products. However, this development changed products both in appearance and interaction, and as a result our relation with products in a less engaging one (Borgmann, 1987). Take for example the kitchen balance. Whereas in the old days the balance allowed someone to weigh his food by keeping the scale in balance using different weights, nowadays we simply put our food on a thin compact platter and read the result on a tiny display. Although Borgmann refers to the change from 'things' to 'devices', the above mentioned examples of the record and the CD player show that this change to a lesser engagement also occurs between old and new devices.

Nowadays technological products place a heavy burden on the human intellect.

Sometimes intellect does not even suffice to operate products and clairvoyance is needed, for example when you accidentally change the settings of the balance from kilos to English pounds and you want to undo that change. The electronics used in products are 'intangible', i.e. they do not relate to our mechanical world.

This implies that the functional parts of a product no longer impose a specific appearance or way of interaction. Technological products cause considerable usability problems making manuals indispensable.

These changes in products have social consequences too, because products are inextricably intertwined with society. A product arises in a social context and consequently is a reflection of that society. Moreover, a product is a vehicle to actively steer the society. The open office layout and furnishing that originated in the twenties, enabled the ideas of scientific management like efficiency, as introduced by Frederick Taylor (Forty, 1986). Present day computers support our market-economy and management system, where time is money and knowledge is power. The technology push stimulates mass consumption and diminishes social engagement.

Do the advantages counterbalance the disadvantages like severe environmental problems, the increasing gap between rich and poor, and our evaporating values that we experience every day in TV shows like "Jerry Springer" and "Cops"? We cannot set aside technology, but we can decide which kind of society we want products to support (Borgmann, 1987; Saul, 1997). We can only discuss in a social context what we consider 'good' design.

In the remaining part of this text, I try to define what I consider 'good' design and show

an alternative for products like the CD player and the digital balance.

My proposal comprises three levels: the society, the product and the design discipline. Do not expect a rational discourse resulting in 'the truth', because you will see later on that I do not believe in universality. Moreover, this is a conference on design and emotion, and not on design and rationality. Therefore,

I follow Borgmann's strategy of a deictic discourse, and hope- 41
fully can seduce you to open yourself to these proposals.

A social framework for product design

"Maintaining a sense of identity and stability through all these changes (in the world and in our communities, C.H.) is not easy. Yet that is what we must do if we are to retain our equilibrium, our self-respect and, above all, our humanity. Despite occasional lapses, in advanced societies we are gradually coming to our senses. We are realising that it is time to concentrate on the important things in life, on basic values and qualities."

Stefano Marzano
(1996)

Borgmann and Saul plead for a similar approach. I believe that these three are right on target. Respect, humanism and engagement are values that could preserve the advantages that technology brought us, and simultaneously show us a way to deal with our problems.

Respect means respect for the man as a whole. When you want an engaging society with engaging products, you cannot only focus on man's cognitive skills. His perceptual-motor and emotional skills are indispensable. This implies that respect refers to the individual. Although we are all humans, have common sensorial and physical aspects and live in the same world, we all have our personal history in life and our own physical, emotional and rational characteristics. Nevertheless, we can only be individuals in a social context, by respecting each other.

An engaging context for experience

When we place respect, humanism and engagement in a design context, it means that we should not focus on only the user or only the product, but on the relation between the user and the product. Design should shift from creating products to creating contexts for experience. Instead of having to instruct a 'black box', the user should be seduced and supported to enjoy listening to music, cooking, ... with all senses (Overbeeke e al., 1999). Because experiences are individual, these contexts are preferably open systems that evolve during interaction with a specific user.

By designing contexts for experience instead of simply products, the focus shifts from the result of interaction, e.g. the music, the weight, towards the involvement during interaction, e.g. putting on a record and listening to music, weighing food. This means that the designer's emphasis should not merely lie on creating a beautiful, pleasing product

in appearance, but expand to creating a beautiful, engaging interaction with a product. Let me try to visualise what I mean with a context for experience. The next design examples made by our second year design students, integrate aesthetic appearance with aesthetic interaction, given a specific context.

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Soft drink containers

These three containers were especially designed for the soft drinks Ice Coffee, Ginger Ale and Dr. Pepper (from left to right). The student did not only express the taste etc., but they also enhanced the character of the drink in package elicits firmness and strength by its dark colours, the two handles and the small opening to slow down the drinking speed. The Ginger Ale container reflects freshness and sharpness, through the taut silver-coloured funnel and the small pinchable capsules that prohibit consuming large amounts of liquids. Finally, Dr. Pepper is bottled in a cheerful, exuberant reddish bulgy shape with flexible straws to attain a playful, sweet and exciting drinking experience.

Naturally, this is a design exercise to train expressivity. It is doubtful if the disposable package for Ginger Ale is an appropriate answer to our environmental problems. Nevertheless, the approach as such supports durability, because engagement enhances our care for products and diminishes disposal (Verbeek et al., 1998).

Personal pagers

In this exercise students designed a pager that could send the simple message "I need you" without using any words. The pager was context dependent, which implied that the sender could indicate the urgency of his message and the receiver could indicate his accessibility. Furthermore, the pager was user dependent, which meant that the pager was designed to contact two specific students. In appearance and interaction it had to express the users and the functions.

unit, thus prohibiting the balloon to grow. Yannic's central unit twists simultaneously, blocking the passage of air and complicating the squeezing activity.

This example shows that a context for experience addresses aspects that are ignored in 'traditional' technological products.

Changing the design discipline: new methods, relations and tools

To implement the basic ideas behind the social framework and the context for experience, means changing research, education, the profession and tools.

Research

Having respect for the individual user and enhancing his experiences implies that designers need to study the experiential horizon of the individual. Gaver and Dunne (1999) introduced 'Cultural Probes' being one way to explore this horizon. By offering visually tempting packages composed of maps, postcards, a camera, a photo album and a diary they showed their respect to the users and invited them to actively participate in the design process.

Furthermore, talking about contexts to evoke experiences, implicitly denies the existence of absolute, generally applicable rules. A context is based on a specific situation, with specific persons having specific intentions etcetera. I propose that the emphasis is placed on context dependence and subtlety. The classical highly controlled experiment that tries to uncover 'the truth' through falsification kills

The pager from Yannic consists of two personal pumps, one to contact Eva (yellow sphere) and one to contact Cees (blue cube), and a central unit with bars and a balloon. To contact Eva, Yannic places the yellow sphere on the central unit and pumps. The force he uses to squeeze the pump indicates the urgency of his message. A comparable unit that is owned by Eva, is reacting to Yannic's call, by a growing balloon that starts emitting a red light. When Eva does not want to be disturbed, she twists the bars from her central

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expression Eva according to Yannic

both aspects. Why do designers not use their strength and design, explore, test, Why not replace research for search, exchange the laboratory for the centre of society, and provoke users to express their thoughts, feelings and dreams (Sanders, 1999).

Education

Respecting the man as a whole means respecting his cognitive, perceptual-motor and emotional skills. This applies to both the user and the designer. Therefore, I believe a design programme should be tuned to these three aspects. The cognitive skills can be refined through knowledge and critical thinking, e.g. engineering and philosophy. The perceptual-motor skills can be improved by educating the senses: show the students that they can trust their senses and train them in subtlety and refinement. The emotional skills can be expanded in courses that teach students to explore the poetical power of appearance and movements. For example, why not give design students dance and acting classes?

Profession

Respect and engagement can also be incorporated during the design process, as Gaver and Dunne show with their 'Cultural Probes'. To intensify these aspects, I propose a libertarian relation between the designer and the user. A libertarian approach emphasises the freedom and personal responsibility of every individual. This means that the designer is no longer placed above the users, but he is one of them. This approach does by no means imply the absence of order or discipline. It only rejects an omnipotent designer. In such a voluntary collaboration the designer can use his own passion to resonate, so to speak, to the passion of the individuals.

Tools

The traditional tools primarily support the exploration of appearance, for instance the flat and static character of paper when sketching complicates the exploration of interaction. To create a 'context for experience', the designer is helped with tools that allow him to explore the poetry of interaction directly in 3D. Gestural sketching could be such a tool (Hummels et al., in press).

Does 'good' design exist? Conclusions and discussion

As you might have concluded from my proposal, I do not believe in an absolute criterion that defines 'good' design. Rather, I see 'good' design as an ideal that one strives for. A context for experience can be considered 'good' for a specific person, provided that it is not at the expense of others. That last remark indicates exactly the bottleneck, because 'the expense' is a relative notion; Greenpeace employs a different definition than Shell.

Nevertheless, in this paper I mentioned several aspects I consider significant for 'good' design:

- respect and freedom for the individual user as a whole and his social environment including people and nature.
- seductive engaging contexts for experience that are aesthetically pleasing for all senses although not per definition easy to use
- a diversity of solutions that have an open character and can evolve during interaction.

I realise that the approach that I advocate is not an easy one. However, I do hope it is a challenging and tempting approach which several designers, researchers and educators are willing to try and evaluate.

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